

SOLID STATE FERMENTATION: PROCESSES, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

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The rise of agro-industrial residues as waste has become a global environment issue. A sustainable approach to valorize these residues and generate bioactive compounds, contributing to circular economy is solid-state fermentation (SSF) process [1,2]. SSF includes limited utilization of water or lack of free water for growth of microorganisms such as fungi and bacteria on the agro-waste as substrate, producing various compounds such as enzymes, proteins and peptides, biosurfactants, and other secondary metabolites [3]. Moreover, lower water content guarantees less contamination and higher yield of the products. SSF emulates the natural condition of growth, specifically in fungi that need limited moisture and attachment surface for growth [4,5].

Agro-industrial wastes are highly loaded with sugars, proteins, and minerals which enhance the growth conditions in presence of restricted moisture for microbial growth. Various agro-industrial by-products have been documented for their efficient utilization as substrate in SSF such as wheat bran, rice bran and husk, oat bran, maize stalk, grape stalk, peanut oil cake, olive oil cake, olive pomace, rape seed cake, fruit (mango, pomegranate, banana, apple) peels, fruit (apple, tamarind, plum, apricot) seeds, soybean meal, sugarcane bagasse, molasses, to name a few [6–8]. These provide sufficient nutrient, generally after mechanical, enzymatic, and acidic pretreatment which makes the raw material more susceptible to breakdown and readily available for consumption by microorganism. Notable microbial species that have been used for SSF include fungi- *Aspergillus niger*, *A. terreus*, *A. oryzae* [9,10], *Penicillium minioluteum*, *A. fumigatus*, *Trichoderma asperellum*, *T. viride*, *Kluyveromyces marxianus* and *Ceratocytis fimbriata*, *Rhizopus oligosporus*, *Beauveria bassiana*, *Monascus anka*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Hanseniaspora valbyensis*, *Hanseniaspora uvarum*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Mucor subtilissimus* *Penicillium sp.* [11], *Ganoderma lucidum*, *Pleurotus ostreatus* [12], *Agaricus bisporus* [13], *A. blazei*, *Trametes versicolor* [14]; actinomycetes- *Streptomyces gilvosporeus* *S. rimosus*; bacteria- *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Arthrospira platensis*, *Bacillus subtilis* [15], *B. amyloliquefaciens* *Lacticaseibacillus casei* and *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus* [16–18].

An overview of Solid-State Fermentation

Different factors are responsible for extruding the desired products from these microorganisms through SSF, majorly including the substrate, particle size, inoculum size and its type, pH, temperature, and moisture content and water activity [17]. Low cost and ease of availability of the substrate is crucial. Furthermore, the nutrient profile and heterogeneity of the substrate becomes the decisive factor in determining the suitable substrate for production of a specific bioactive compound. The substrate should have sufficient porosity to allow air movement and proper adherence of the microbes on the surface [16,17]. Second factor is particle size of the substrate which determines the particle's surface area-to-volume ratio. In order to ensure optimal heat and mass transfer, an ideal ratio is essential to facilitate efficient gaseous exchange. The particle size determines the void space taken up by air as the transfer of oxygen through this space is essential for the proper growth of the microorganism. Smaller particle size is generally taken into account, as it provides greater surface area for attachment, nevertheless much smaller particle size may hinder with oxygen transfer due to less void space and substrate agglomeration [17].

Optimized values of inoculum are essential for microbial growth. In case of fungal fermentation, spore inoculum is preferred due to its enhanced shelf life and homogeneity. Furthermore, pH of the solid-state medium determines the growth of specific type of microorganism as bacteria grow at pH near neutral values, fungus and yeast at slightly acidic pH while actinomycetes grow above neutral pH. Furthermore, optimum moisture (30-80%) and water content of the substrate aids in proper dissolution of minerals and nutrients for microbial growth. Higher moisture level hampers the growth by obstructing the pores and slowing the oxygen transfer rate. Though SSF has been successfully utilized for various categories of microorganisms, but bacteria have higher water activity requirement of 0.8 A_w in comparison to fungi and yeast (0.5 A_w), therefore, bacteria are considered less suitable for SSF.

SSF process needs specifically designed bioreactors for optimum growth and bioactive compound production. The most commonly used are tray fermenters with multiple metallic trays to hold the solid substrate, rolling bed fermenters with multiple rotating drums and sprinklers to maintain moisture content and heat dissipation, and plug flow fermenters [19]. Despite the higher yield of bioactives in SSF, yet numerous challenges restrict the extensive use of this mode of fermentation at commercial level, of which the major hinderance is the scale up process due to heterogenous nature of substrate which further culminates into non-uniform heat and mass transfer. In addition, downstream processing of the product is a tedious task as metabolites are diffused in the solid substrate matrix[17,18].

The constraints in SSF process are being addressed by researchers worldwide as it is not limited to only produce low value compounds but can be utilized for production of higher content of pharmaceutical compound's at large scale at lower cost in a sustainable manner. For this, large scale production can be obtained through novel advanced bioreactors with improved heat dissipation and mass transfer features overcoming current obstacles.

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